

ENVIRONMENTAL AND HEALTH DATABASES 1

Deliverable D2.1

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HIGH HORIZONS – D2.1

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviations	Definition/Description
SQL	Structured Query Language used to create and manage relational databases
NoSQL	Not Only Structured Query Language describes a type of database design
ERA5	The 5 th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document provides an overview of the 1st version of the environmental database in fulfilment with deliverable D2.1. In addition, it assesses database design to evaluate which approach would be the most beneficial given the data requirement of the HIGH Horizons project. Further, it presents the metadata of the variables with relevant sharing rules for both environment and health data available for the project. The work here is in line with the data management plan presented in D1.4.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable can be seen as a keystone of the project, providing data management for a number of other deliverables within the WP2. But it also has a far-reaching scope influencing other deliverables in WP3 and WP4. Some of the notable connections are:

- D2.3 Analysis of Environmental Health Data 1
- D3.2 Indicators selected
- D4.1 training on use of monitoring indicators.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is structured into 6 main chapters. First an overview of the background of database design is presented in **Chapter 2**. Then, the categories of designs are used to categorize existing databases to evaluate what the most common design is in **Chapter 3**. Next, the database requirements, design and meta-data for HIGH Horizons is presented in **Chapter 4**. In addition, in **Chapter 5** open-source secondary supplementary data is described. Future work for later in the project is outlined in **Chapter 6**, before concluding in **Chapter 7**.

2 Background of database design

A database is defined as: “an organized collection of data and information or interrelated data collected at one place”¹. One way to assess databases is to categorize them in 5 different types: *Hierarchical database, Network database, Object-Orient database, Relational database, and NoSQL database.*

Hierarchical database. A hierarchical database is described by Some et al., (2004) as ‘*The database canonically implements the data hierarchy. A hierarchy, in this case, can be thought of as a tree structure.*’ An example of a hierarchical database is the background of Microsoft office products that rely on XML².

Network database. Within network database design individual pieces of data can be linked to one or more other pieces of data^{3,4}. This is seen as a more intuitive type of database design than Hierarchical databases, allowing for multiple interconnecting relationships to be built between data. Both Network and Hierarchical database management systems were popular prior to the development of relational databases².

Object-Orient database. This database type is designed to work with object-oriented programming languages for example Java. The concept is that every piece of information stored in the database is an object and then objects with similar attributes are stored in groups known as classes⁵. For example, if you had data about a washing machine and a dishwasher this could be grouped in a class about appliances.

Relational database. This type of database is often the most common data management system. Relational databases rely on by standard SQL (Structured Query Language) and is based around a table design¹. An advantage of relational databases is the ‘*Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability (ACID)*’ which ensures updates to the database are reliable and not a cause of conflict within the data structure⁶.

NoSQL database. Not Only SQL databases are designed to store data in a non-tabular way, for example storing a collection of documents, or a series of different data. These databases allow for a more flexible approach to data storage⁷. Many types of NoSQL databases are now optimized for cloud computing and can provide security in updates through the base system in comparison to ACID^{6,7}.

3 Typology of existing data centres and repositories

Using the categories presented in section 2, allows for the evaluation of what the most common type of database is providing evidence to how the HIGH Horizon's database should be designed. A list of data centres and repositories for the field of the geosciences has been compiled by the Royal Meteorological Society Geoscience Data Journal⁸. This field is overall mostly in line with the project here given its interdisciplinary nature; appropriate centres from the list are included in table 1.

Table 1: List of common data centres and repositories termed databases categorized by database type.

Name of Database	Database Type	Region of Coverage	Reference
Australian National Data Service	Type of NoSQL which is stated to have a Registry Interchange Format - Collections and Services (RIF-CS) design	Australia	⁹
Centre for Environmental Data Analysis Archive (CEDA)	Type of NoSQL has a document structure.	United Kingdom	¹⁰
Copernicus Data Store (CDS)	Type of Hierarchical Database with archival retrieval	Global	¹¹
Figshare	Type of NoSQL database for documents	Global	¹²
National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) Research Data Archive (RDA)	Type of Relational Database	Global	^{13,14}

Name of Database	Database Type	Region of Coverage	Reference
National Geoscience Data Centre (NGDC)	Type of NoSQL database for documents	Global	15
NOAA National Climatic Data Centre (NCDC)	Type of Hierarchical Database with archival retrieval	Global	16
PANGAEA	Type of NoSQL database for documents	Global	17
UFZ Data Investigation Portal	Type of NoSQL for documents	Global	18
Zenodo	Type of NoSQL for documents	Global	19

4 HIGH Horizons database

4.1 Database requirements

There are 3 main categories of data required in the HIGH Horizons project can be grouped as: *Health, Contextual and Environmental*. Previous research in the maternal health and child health field has for example demonstrated that health outcomes are influenced by extreme heat (environmental), but this is modulated by contextual factors such as socio-economic status and age²⁰. The main database requirements for HIGH Horizons are:

- Decentralized design within country storage so sensitive data agreements are not violated;
- The storage of global environmental data that can be merged with the health data;
- The storage where possible of aggregated country data (health and contextual factors);
- Sharing of open data and data with data sharing agreements to facilitate analysis collaborations to explore indicators.

4.2 Database design

Given the data sensitivity and security surrounding some of the required data for HIGH Horizons, a decentralized database design like that of a NoSQL database for documents has been chosen, an entity-relationship diagram of this can be seen in figure 1.

Note: An entity relationship diagram between the different data holders with the need to analysis environmental-health data to come to a consensus on global heat health indicators for maternal and child health. 1..0 indicates that just that institute has access to the data, 1..1 indicates access is available with a data agreement, whilst 1..n indicates access across partners.

Figure 1: Entity relationship diagram between data holders of HIGH Horizons

4.3 Health data

Health data considers all variables that indicate a certain medical outcome. Most of the health data used in HIGH Horizons is highly sensitive data. Where possible data is planned to be shared using data sharing agreements and spatial and temporal aggregation techniques. In comparison, where this is not possible, methodological sharing and the use of open-source software will allow for the robustness of methods to be consistent across partner organisations. It is felt that this is an important step in achieving one of the objectives of the HIGH Horizons project to develop global indicators for climate change, heat, and maternal and child health. Here, the health data for each country is described. It is hoped that by the end of the project data for Kenya and Greece¹ will also be present.

Sweden: The data used in HIGH Horizons is from the Swedish Population Registry. 92% of the population is covered and it provides useful information of pregnancy and early childhood. The data starts in the 1970s, approximately 100,000 births per year.

Italy: The HIGH Horizons project has access to the Lazio Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (CEDAP) which includes data on all births between the 2001 and the 2021 in the region, approximately 40,000 births per year.

South Africa: Data comes from one health district (Tshwane) and one sub-district in Johannesburg (Region F). One example is the Rahima Moosa Mother and Child Hospital site, including approximately 16,000 paediatric admissions, and more than 17,000 births annually since the early 2000s.

Summary tables of health and confounding data can be found in Annex.

¹ The partner from Greece, University of Thessaly, will join the HIGH Horizons consortium soon thanks to the [Hop On grant](#) awarded within call HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-07-01.

4.4 Contextual data

Similar restrictions are present with contextual data, which includes factors such as socio-economic status of a mother or residential address. Therefore, sharing is only possible between institutes where the identity is completely anonymized. Again, the contextual data is described below.

Sweden: Everyone in Sweden has a unique identifier that allows for linking with the National Patient Register (for maternal and neonatal health outcomes) and Statistics Sweden for socio-economic and residential information.

Italy: Record links within Lazio regional hospital information system provides a link to information on childbirth with sociodemographic variables.

South Africa: Past birth information, age of the mother and health conditions are all contextual factors included in the South African data.

Summary tables of health and confounding data can be found in Annex A.

4.5 Environmental data

There are less restrictions around environmental data than health data because it does not have sensitivity challenges. Where possible it is the hope of the project that observation datasets can be used from weather stations, as these are seen as potentially more accurate than reanalysis, satellite, or other types of post-processed datasets. The environmental data is summarized below per country.

Sweden: The Swedish environmental data models several air pollution and ambient temperature variables using a machine learning method known as a Random Regression Forest. This allows for high resolution data 0.01X0.01 grid, with a daily temporal range to be created. This is modelled using a few secondary data sources such as including satellites, dispersion models, land cover, meteorology, and population data.

Italy: The Lazio region has a similar database to the Swedish, being created by the same team.

South Africa: South Africa will where possible use observed weather data from the Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO).

5 Secondary data

In addition to observed data and high-resolution data from HIGH Horizons, a number of secondary sources of data has been collected to allow for further analysis of chosen global heat health indicators to take place if capacity permits.

5.1 Health and socio-economic datasets

There are multiple sources of health and contextual/socio-economic secondary data. One is the global burden of disease which has the mission to quantify disease loss, to lead to an improvement of health services²¹. The data is contributed to and analysed by a consortium of over 9,000 researchers worldwide. The data includes high level socio-economic data (such as prevalence of smoking, types of wealth indexes, crude mortality rate) at a country level which could provide key insights into contextual factors that influence heat outcomes²¹. Another similar source of data is Our World in Data, providing data on aspects such as hunger, indications of levels of poverty, sanitation, and air pollution²². In addition, these datasets provide high-level health outcomes that may give a more global view of heat impacts on maternal, neonatal and child health. Population data is available from the Oak Ridge National Laboratory known as Land Scan from 2000 to 2021^{23,24}. Further, data from the demographic health surveys (DHS), multiple cluster indicator survey (MICs) and Indepth Health and Demographic survey sites could be explored²⁵⁻²⁷.

5.2 Reanalysis datasets

To supplement available environmental data HIGH Horizons will make use of open-source reanalysis data. A reanalysis dataset combines a range of observations (i.e., satellite data and weather station data) with numerical weather prediction data via data assimilation²⁸. Limitations using this dataset are most apparent at high elevations, in dense urban areas and along coastlines, and it

should be noted that limitations are different depending on the variables considered²⁸.

Out of the reanalysis products available, the project will rely on ERA5 to start with. ERA5 is this is a state-of-the-art dataset that provides global gridded data every 1 hour at a 0.25x0.25° grid scale, providing data for regions where observations are sparse²⁸. This includes parts of Africa which is a region of focus of the project. In addition, ERA5 is the only product available open source that provides data for Mean Radiant Temperature and the thermal comfort index the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) as part of ERA5-HEAT²⁹. Mean Radiant Temperature is also required to calculate Wet Bulb Globe Temperature an international standard for heat stress³⁰. Both, the UTCI and WBGT are thermal comfort indices of interest in this project.

Table 2: Available open-source reanalysis datasets to supplement environmental data used in HIGH Horizons.

Reanalysis Dataset	Provider	DOI
ERA5	ECMWF	doi:10.24381/cds.e2161bac
MERRA-2	NASA	doi:10.5067/VJAFPLI1CSIV
JRA-55	Japanese Meteorological Agency	doi:10.2151/jmsj.2015-001
CFSR	NOAA	doi:10.1175/2010BAMS3001.1

5.3 Remote sensing datasets

In the future, HIGH Horizons may use remote sensing datasets to further supplement environmental data. Remote sensing datasets such as those from satellites would allow for the assessment of factors such as land surface temperature, land-cover and ‘greenness’. It has previously been suggested by maternal health studies that greenness might be an influential factor in some birth outcomes^{31,32}. Sources of vegetation cover include data from NASA satellites and Copernicus satellites^{33,34}.

6 Future work

It is early days in the data curation and data analysis of the project. Currently access is only available for analysis of South African, Swedish and Italian data. We are working with the Kenyan partner to evaluate their data and this will be included in a future update of the database and analytics. In addition, we have a new Greek partner and their data will be included in a future update. New data may become available within the lifetime of the project, and where there is capacity and relevance this will be added. In addition, there is a close link between intensity of heatwaves and soil moisture content³⁵ this could be an interesting pathway to explore at a later date during the project.

7 Conclusions

In this deliverable, the categories of potential database designs are reviewed. In addition, existing data centres and repositories are typed to consider how they map to the database designs (Chapter 2 and 3). This was explored so that the database requirements of the HIGH Horizons project could be mapped to an existing database management design, for robust data storage. The most important requirement of the HIGH Horizons project is to maintain security for sensitive data. The final design of the decentralized database is present in figure 1 with the flows of data indicated between partner organizations.

The data available at an individual country level is outlined in terms of health, contextual and environmental categories (Chapter 4). This demonstrates the scope of the data that could go on to become indicators in the HIGH Horizons project. This also gives an overview of some of the existing literature that has evaluated this data, which is also beneficial to the project objectives. In addition, a table of the metadata for each countries health and contextual factors is provided in the annex of this report.

To supplement individual country data with the vision of making data available more in line with a potentially global indicator, secondary data sources have been collected for all types of data (Chapter 5). This data will be analysed in line with partners capacity and could be used as an addition to the already available individual country data. In addition, the use of this data will become clearer after the achievement of deliverables 3.2 and 2.3. Finally, the future work that will take place within the theme of this deliverable is highlighted and this will be updated on in deliverable 2.2.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1 – Health and contextual data for Sweden

Table 3: Sweden health data overview

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Resuscitation measures - Acidosis correction, minutes	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - acupuncture	1=Yes	1994-	Cannot be calculated
Prenatal diagnostics, amniocentesis	1=Yes	1994-	Under reported
Prenatal diagnostics, amniocentesis, note	1=Without remarks; 2=With remarks	1994-	Under reported
Prenatal diagnostics, amniocentesis, note, date for sample	Alphanumeric date	1994-	Under reported
Pain relief - Other. Pharmacological code for this pain relief should be stated in SMLKOD.	1=Yes	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Assessment of Apgar score at 1 min of age	01-10	1973-	70's 1.6%; 80's 1.3%; 90's 0.8%; 2000's 0.6%
Assessment of Apgar score at 10 min of age	01-10	1973-	70's 85.1%; 80's 50.3%; 90's 18.2%; 2000's 3.0%
Assessment of Apgar score at 5 min of age	01-10	1973-	70's 11.4%; 80's 4.3%; 90's 0.9%; 2000's 0.7%
Year of birth of the child		1973-	No missing
Scope of working hours at first antenatal care visit	1=Full time; 2=Part time; 3=No	1982-	80's 28.3%; 90's 21.8%; 2000's 14.1%
Maternal diseases, lung disease / asthma (self-reported)	1=Actual or previous; 2=Previous (only for the period 1990-93); Blank=No or Missing information	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Pain relief - bath	1=Yes	1994-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 1 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 10 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 11 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 12 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 2 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Infants' diagnosis 3 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 4 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 5 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 6 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 7 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1982-1991, 1999-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Infants' diagnosis 8 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 9 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' diagnosis 1-12 (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems. The child's diagnosis 1-12 in text string.	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Number of antenatal care visits (summary)	1-32 or blank	1995-	90's minimum 36.1%; 2000's minimum 6.8%
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care interventions (KÅÅ). Infant's surgical or care interventions 1-12 as string variable.	1973-86, 1999-	
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and	1973-86, 1999-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
	Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).		
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-86, 1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-86, 1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-86, 1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Infants' surgical code or care interventions 1-12 (KVÅ Codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Day of birth of the Infant	Alphanumeric date	1973-	
Day of birth of the Infant	Numeric date	1973-	
Foetal presentation irrespective of delivery mode	See appendix for codes before 1999. 1999 and onwards 1 = Occiput anterior presentation; 4 = Occiput posterior presentation; 6 = Breech or footling breech presentation; 0 = Other foetal presentation	1982-	70's 8.8%; 80's 47.0%; 90's 12.2%; 2000's 4.7%
Length of the Infant, cm	20-79	1973-	70's 0.3%; 80's 1.0%; 90's 1.7%; 2000's 1.3%
Information about number of babies	1=singleton; 2=multiple birth	1973-	

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Parity and number of births in a multiple birth	Position 1 : birth order number for multiple births; Position 2 : Number of children in the actual birth	1973-	
The Infant's personal identity number. Date of birth is available from the patient record. The unique identifying civic registration number is retrieved from Statistics Sweden (SCB; birth registry)		1973-	
The Infant's personal identity number, quality	0 = Valid; 5 = Stillborn; 8, 9 = Invalid civic registration number	1973-	Exists for everyone
Estimated date of delivery from the first day of the last menstrual period (LMP). Note: Can be calculated from the variable SMDAT for the period 1973-81.	Alphanumeric date	1982-	80's 14.7%; 90's 12.1%; 2000's 10.3%
Estimated date of delivery according to ultrasound examination	Alphanumeric date	1982-	80's 68.7%; 90's 22.5%; 2000's 13.2%
Infants' discharge date from hospital. 1973-1981 / 1982: date of discharge from delivery ward/postnatal care ward. 1982-1998: definitive discharge date from the hospital around the time of childbirth. 1999 and beyond: date of discharge from hospital	Alphanumeric date	1973-	70's 0.1%; 80's 2.8%; 90's 5.5%; 2000's 6.5%
Infant's mode of discharge from the hospital	1973-1988 1 = Home; 2 = To the paediatric clinic; 3 = Other clinic; 4 = Other address; 1982 / 83-1989 / 90 1 = Home; 2 = Other address; 1990 / 91- 1 = Home; 2 = To another address; 3 = Still hospitalized at 28 days; 1999 and beyond	1973-	

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
	1 = Still hospitalized at 28 days		
The Infant's birth weight, grams. Note; Until 2011, birth weights <300 g were registered as blank for live-born. From 2012 weights <270 g are registered as blank for live born children. Weights> 6999 are blanked for all babies (live- and stillborn)	For live born babies: until year 2011: 300-6999, from year 2012: 270-6999. For stillborn babies: min-max	1973-	70's 0.1%; 80's 0.5%; 90's 0.3%; 2000's 0.3%
Cervical tear. Note: information registered through check box in the case notes. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's marital status. Note: From 1982 there is information about the mother's family situation in the variable FAMSIT	1=Unmarried; 2=Married; 3= Previously married	1973-1981	70's 7.4%; 80's 11.6%;
Prenatal diagnostics, chorionic villus sampling (CVS)	1=Yes	1994-	Under reported
Prenatal diagnostics, chorionic villus sampling (CVS), note	1=Without remarks; 2=With remarks	1994-	Under reported
Prenatal diagnostics, chorionic villus sampling (CVS), sampling date	Alphanumeric date	1994-	Under reported
Age at death, days. Information from the Cause of Death Register / AVI. Only the newborn period.	Only the newborn period, i.e. day 0-27	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diseases, diabetes mellitus (self-reported). No gestational diabetes.	1 = Current or earlier; 2 = Earlier (only during the period 1990-93); Blank = No or missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Survival, newborn period	1 = Stillborn; 2 = Death within 0-6 days; 3 = Dead within 7-27 days	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Stillborn according to the patient file	1=Before onset of labour; 2=During labour	1973-	

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Time of death, Infant	HHMM (hours-minutes)	1973-	
Elective / planned or emergency caesarean section. Information about childbirth started with caesarean section before the onset of labour pains.	1=Elective; 2=Emergency	1999-	Not filled out consequently the same way. Insecurity around calculating missing.
Pain Relief - Epidural Anaesthesia (EDA)	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diseases, epilepsy (self-reported)	1 = Current or earlier; 2 = Earlier (only during the period 1990-93); Blank = No or missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
The family situation. Note: For the years 1973-1982, the variable CIVIL can be used.	1= Living together with the father of the Infant; 2 = Single (except 1990-1994); 3 = Other family situation (this category includes single mothers during the period 1990-1994)	1982-	80's 9.3%; 90's 8.2%; 2000's 5.9%
Healthy Infant examined at the postnatal ward. Note: Although this information is filled in, babies can have ICD codes in BDIAGNOS.	1 = Z00.1A Healthy Infant examined at the postnatal ward; 2 = Other diagnoses	1999-	
Childbirth started with labour induction	1=Yes	1990-	Information of how labour started (the variables FLINDUKT, SECFORE, VAGINAL) is missing for 10.4% during the 90's and for 1.1% during the 2000's
Surgery during childbirth (other than Caesarean section, vacuum extraction, forceps)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 1 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
	Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).		
Mother's surgical or care intervention 10 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 11 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 12 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 2 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 3 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-1986, 1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 4 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1973-1986, 1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 5 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Mother's surgical or care intervention 6 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 7 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 8 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care intervention 9 during childbirth (KÅÅ code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care Intervention (KVÅ).	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Spontaneous onset of labour	1=Yes	1990-	Information of how labour started (the variables FLINDUKT, SECFORE, VAGINAL) is missing for 10.4% during the 90's and for 1.1% during the 2000's
Father's citizenship (information from the register of total population (RTB))	Plain text	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Time of birth	HHMM (hours-minutes; in some instances only HH exists)	1973-	70's 0.2%; 80's 0.7%; 90's 0.8%; 2000's 0.9%
Mother's diagnosis / surgical intervention or care intervention during pregnancy (ICD or KVÅ code)	ICD8 codes 1973-1986; ICD9 codes 1987-1989, as well as surgical and intervention codes 1982-1989	1973-1989	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Mother's diagnosis / surgical intervention or care intervention during pregnancy (ICD or KVÅ code)	ICD8 codes 1973-1986; ICD9 codes 1987-1989, as well as surgical and intervention codes 1982-1989	1973-1989	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis / surgical intervention or care intervention during pregnancy (ICD or KVÅ code)	ICD8 codes 1973-1986; ICD9 codes 1987-1989, as well as surgical and intervention codes 1982-1989	1973-1989	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis / surgical intervention or care intervention during pregnancy (ICD or KVÅ code). Note: information available only for the period 1982-1989.	ICD8 codes 1973-1986; ICD9 codes 1987-1989, as well as surgical and intervention codes 1982-1989	1973-1989	Cannot be calculated
Pregnancy length / gestational age best estimate in days. Note: The pregnancy length is calculated based on pre-defined conditions with regard to dating based on primary ultrasound, secondary last menstrual period, etc. (see variable GRMETOD).	154-321	1973-	70's 0.4%; 80's 0.3%; 90's 0.2%; 2000's 0.1%
Pregnancy length / gestational age in days in addition to completed weeks according to patient file information. Note: To determine the length of pregnancy in days, it is recommended to use the calculated variable GRDBS.	0-6	1994-	90's 46.3%; 2000's 1.8%
Pregnancy length, method of estimation (basis for the calculated variables GRVBS and GRDBS)	1-12	1973-	
Pregnancy length / gestational age best estimate in completed weeks. Note: The pregnancy length is calculated based on pre-defined conditions with regard to e.g. dating based on primary ultrasound, secondary last menstrual period (LMP), etc. (see variable GRMETOD).	22-45	1973-	70's 0.4%; 80's 0.3%; 90's 0.2%; 2000's 0.1%

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Pregnancy length / gestational age in completed weeks according to patient file. Note: In order to determine the pregnancy length in weeks, it is recommended to use the calculated variable GRVBS.	Minimum-maximum	1973-	70's 2.3%; 80's 4.0%; 90's 2.4%; 2000's 0.6%
In twin births amniotic wall. Note: Other values may occur.	0; 2; 4	1994-	
Resuscitation - heart compressions, minutes	0-99	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Head circumference, paediatric, cm	15-45	1973-	70's 1.6%; 80's 2.2%; 90's 5.2%; 2000's 4.6%
Mother's diseases, chronic hypertension (self-reported)	1 = Current or earlier; 2 = Earlier (only during the period 1990-93); Blank = No or missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - hypnosis	1=Yes	1982-	Cannot be calculated
ICD version			
Pain relief - no pharmacological pain relief	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Admission date to the delivery ward. Note: when calculating days of hospital care, the child's date of birth and the date of discharge are used.	Alphanumeric date	1973-	70's 0.1%; 80's 2.2%; 90's 2.5%; 2000's 0.8%
Date of admission. First antenatal care visit	Alphanumeric date	1995-	90's 34.6%; 2000's 6.3%
Pain relief - infiltration (local anaesthetics)	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Resuscitation - ventilation after intubation, minutes	0-99	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - No pain relief	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Clinic /Activity area	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's list of areas of activities. However, other codes may be used as well.	1999-	90's 34.1%; 2000's 21.7%

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Episiotomy	1 = Right (medio-lateral); 2 = Median (medial); 3 = Left (medio-lateral)	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Tear - Clitoris. Note: information noted in the check box in the patient file. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Sex of the Infant	1=Boy; 2=Girl	1973-	
Pain relief - intracutaneous injection of sterile water	1=Yes	1994-	Cannot be calculated
Vitamin K	1=intramuscular (im); 2=orally	1999-	Cannot be calculated
County-municipal assembly according to Statistics Sweden (at the time applicable division). The mother's registered address at the time of giving birth.		1973-	70's 0.2%; 80's 0.2%; 90's 0.5%; 2000's 1.3%
Local registration. Possibility to register information to study more closely at regional or local level.		1982-	
Pain relief - Nitrous oxide	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's age at the time of childbirth. Note: Calculated primarily from the unique civic registration number. Where only the date of birth is available, the age is calculated based on the year and month and where only the year of birth is found, the age is calculated based on this information.	Minimum-maximum	1973-	70's 0.0%; 80's 0.0%; 90's 0.1%; 2000's 0.3%
Mother's diagnosis 1 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Mother's diagnosis 10 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 11 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 12 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 2 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 3 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Mother's diagnosis 4 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 5 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 6 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 7 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 8 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Mother's diagnosis 9 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's diagnosis 1-12 during childbirth (ICD code)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's classification and statistical description of diseases and other health problems. Mother's diagnosis 1-12 during childbirth as text.	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's surgical or care interventions 1-12 in childbirth (KVÅ codes)	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's Classification of Care intervention (KÅÅ). Mother's surgical or care interventions 1-12 as text .	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's birthday	Alphanumeric date	1973-	70's 0.0%; 80's 0.0%; 90's 0.1%; 2000's 0.2%
Mother's birthday	Numeric date	1973-	70's 0.0%; 80's 0.0%; 90's 0.1%; 2000's 0.2%
Mother's country of birth (information from the Register of the Total Population, (RTB))	Plain text	1973-	70's 0.5%; 80's 0.6%; 90's 1.3%; 2000's 1.3%
Listed maternity care codes	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's list of maternity health care codes	1998-	90's 36.7%; 2000's 20.6%

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Birth defect Diagnosis. Note: If the child has ICD 8 or ICD 9 diagnosis in the range 740-759 or ICD10 diagnosis Q00-Q99.	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's length in cm. For the period 1982 / 83-1989 / 90, the information is taken from FV1	100-220	1982-	90's 9.6%; 2000's 7.1%
Large for gestational age (LGA). Note: The estimate has been based on Marsal et al's method. Only singleton babies.	1=Yes; 0=No	1973-	70's 0.5%; 80's 0.8%; 90's 0.6%; 2000's 0.5%
Mother's citizenship (information from the register of the total population, (RTB))	Plain text	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's unique civic registration number		1973-	Missing for 0.5%
Mother's unique civic registration number, quality	0 = Valid; 4 = Coordination number; 8, 9 = Invalid civic registration number	1973-	No
Small for gestational age (SGA). Note: The estimate has been based on Marsal et al's method. Only singleton babies.	1=Yes; 0=No	1973-	70's 0.5%; 80's 0.8%; 90's 0.6%; 2000's 0.5%
Mother's date of discharge from the postnatal ward	Alphanumeric date	1973-	70's 0.1%; 80's 1.2%; 90's 1.9%; 2000's 1.7%
Mother's mode of discharge from the postnatal ward	1973-1981 1 = Home; 2 = Other hospital; 3 = Other clinic; 4 = Other address; 5 = Dead, autopsy; 6 = Dead, not autopsy *** 1990 and beyond 1 = Home; 2 = Other care facility	1973-81, 1990-	70's 0.1%; 80's 0.1%; 90's 16.6%; 2000's 1.2%
Mother's weight in kg when enrolling antenatal care. For the years 1982-1989, the information has been calculated on the basis of information on weight at admission for childbirth (MVIKTFV) and weight gain	30-200	1982-1989, 1992-	80's 24.3%; 90-91 100%; 90's 34.5%; 2000's 11.1%

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
(MVIKTKN). For the years 1990-1991, data on weight is missing.			
Mother's weight in kg at the time of childbirth. Note: For the period 1982-1989 weight was coded over 98 kg as 99.	30-200	1982-1989, 1994-	80's 18.1%; 90's 80.3%; 2000's 67.2%
Pain relief - general anaesthesia	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Maternal disease, chronic kidney disease (self-reported)	1 = Current or earlier; 2 = Earlier (only during the period 1990-93); Blank = No or missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Autopsy, the Infant	1=Yes; 2=No	1973-	
Medical intervention for involuntary infertility - Assisted reproductive technology (ART)	1=Yes	1995-	Cannot be calculated
Other intervention for involuntary infertility	1=Yes	1995-	Cannot be calculated
Involuntary infertility, years		1982-	
No medical intervention for involuntary infertility	1=Yes	1995-	Cannot be calculated
Medical intervention for involuntary infertility - intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Medical intervention for involuntary infertility - Surgical	1=Yes	1995-	Cannot be calculated
Medical intervention for involuntary infertility - Ovarian stimulation	1=Yes	1995-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - Paracervical block (PCB)	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Infant's order number. Note: Based on the mother's number of previously born children including current birth. Information taken from Statistics Sweden and MBR.	1-	1973-	
Childbirth order number. Note: Based on the mother's previous number of births including	1-	1973-	

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
current birth. Information taken from Statistics Sweden and MBR.			
Pain relief - Penthrane	1=Yes	1982-1989	Cannot be calculated
Perineal tears. Note: Information from the check box in the patient file. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - Pethidine / morphine derivative	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Weight of the placenta	50-2999	1982-1989	
Date for discontinuation of birth control pill	Alphanumeric date	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - pudendal block	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Tears - Rectum. Note: Information from the check box in the patient file. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Smoking 3 months prior to conception of the current pregnancy. Self-reported information where the mother was asked at the first antenatal care visit	1 = Does not smoke; 2 = 1-9 cig / day; 3 = 10 cig or more / day	1999-	2000's 6.1%. From 2000 the data has been corrected.
Smokes at the first antenatal care visit	1 = Does not smoke; 2 = 1-9 cig / day; 3 = 10 cig or more / day	1982-	80's 12.0%; 90's 5.8%; 2000's 6.2%. From 2000 the data has been corrected.
Smokes at gestational week 30-32	1 = Does not smoke; 2 = 1-9 cig / day; 3 = 10 cig or more / day	1990-	90's 75.2%; 2000's 9.8%
Childbirth ends with caesarean section. Note: The variable SECMARK indicates only caesarean section irrespective of emergency or elective.	1=Yes	1990-	Information on how labour ended is missing for 6.9% during the 90's and for 7.7% during the 2000's
Labour starts with caesarean section	1=Yes	1990-	Information of how labour started (the variables FLINDUKT, SECFOR, VAGINAL) is missing for 10.4% during the 90's and for 1.1% during the 2000's

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Caesarean section, irrespective of emergency or elective. Based on information from the check box in the patient file, diagnosis and medical intervention codes.	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Caesarean section - Elective or non-elective		1982-1989	80's 23.5%
Pain relief - Sedative hypnotics	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Tear - Sphincter. Note: information from the check box in the patient file. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Hospital code, reported	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's list of maternity wards / clinics for current and previous codes	1973-	80's 0.2%; 90's 0.1%; 2000's 0.3%
Hospital code, valid codes for the actual year	According to the National Board of Health and Welfare's list of maternity wards / clinics	1973-	
Maternal diseases, systemic lupus erythematousus (SLE)	1 = Current or earlier; 2 = Earlier (only during the period 1990-93); Blank = No or missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Date for last menstrual period's first day (LMP)	Alphanumeric date	1973-	70's 2.2%; 80's 4.3%; 90's 5.8%; 2000's 8.8%
Use of snuff (tobacco) prior to conception of the current pregnancy. Self-reported information where the mother was asked at the first antenatal care visit	1=Yes; 0=No	1999-	For 2000's 6.2%
Use of snuff (tobacco) at the first antenatal care visit.	1=Yes; 0=No	1999-	For 2000's 6.2%
Use of snuff at gestational week 30-32	1=Yes; 0=No	1999-	2000's 9%

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Pregnancy while using an IUD (intrauterine device)	1=Yes; Blank=No OR information missing	1990-	Cannot be calculated. Information exists in the patient chart since 1982/83, but not in the register until 1990. Most probably under reported.
Pain relief - spinal anaesthesia	1=Yes	1990-	Cannot be calculated
Date for extraction of IUD (intrauterine device)	Alphanumeric date	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Childbirth has ended with vacuum extraction. Note: The variable SUGMARK indicates whether the vacuum extraction device has been used at any time during childbirth.	1=Yes	1990-	Information on how labour ended is missing for 6.9% during the 90's and for 7.7% during the 2000's
Vacuum extraction. Indicates whether vacuum extraction device has been used at some time during childbirth. Based on information from the check box in the patient file, diagnosis and medical intervention codes.	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Childbirth has ended with forceps. Note: The variable TANGMARK indicates whether the forceps has been used at any time during childbirth.	1=Yes	1990-	Information on how labour ended is missing for 6.9% during the 90's and for 7.7% during the 2000's
Forceps. Indicates whether forceps has been used sometime during childbirth. Based on information from the check box in the patient file, codes for diagnosis and interventions .	1=Yes	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Previous pregnancies, number of dead children within 0-6 days	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Previous pregnancies, number of stillbirths	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Previous pregnancies, number of live born children	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Previous pregnancies, number of dead children after 28 days of life	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1982	Cannot be calculated
Previous pregnancies, number of spontaneous abortions (miscarriages)	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Previous pregnancies, number of extrauterine pregnancies	1-9; 9=9 or more; blank= none OR information missing	1982-	Cannot be calculated
Pain relief - Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS)	1=Yes	1994-	Cannot be calculated
Years for previous caesarean sections. Calculated using the mother's previous births in MBR and information in FV1		1973-	
Previous caesarean section. Calculated using the mother's previous births in the MBR and information in FV1	0=No; 1=Yes; blank= information missing	1973-	
Maternal diseases, ulcerative colitis or Mb Crohn, Inflammatory Bowel Disease (self-reported)	1=Currently or previous; 2=Previous (only during the period 1990-93); blank= No OR no information available	1973-	Cannot be calculated
Maternal diseases, repeated urinary tract infections (self-reported)	1=Currently or previous; 2=Previous (only during the period 1990-93); blank= No OR no information available	1973-	Cannot be calculated

Definition - English	Value - English	Timeline - English	Missing - English
Tears - Vagina. Note: Information in the check box in the patient file. Supplemented with ICD code (mother's diagnoses during childbirth)	1=Yes	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Childbirth ends vaginally	1=Yes	1973-	Information of how labour started (the variables FLINDUKT, SECFORE, VAGINAL) is missing for 10.4% during the 90's and for 1.1% during the 2000's
Infant resuscitation measures - Ventilation using mask, minutes	0-99	1999-	Cannot be calculated
Mother's profession at first antenatal care visit. Other information is available, e.g. studies, parental leave and sick leave.	Free text	1982-	During the 80's 21.5%; 90's 18.7%; 2000's 15.0%

9.2 Annex 2 – Health and contextual data for Italy

Table 4: Selection of available Italian health data

Variable	Variable Character
ID of the mother	a.cod_sis_mam
date of the delivery	a.dataparto
citizenship of the mother	a.cittad
education level of the mother	a.titstu
municipality of birth of the mother	a.comnas
gestational age	a.etages
birth weight	a.pesonas
malformations at birth	a.malnas
age of the mother	a.eta_ced
date of discharge of the mother	a.datadim
whether it is a twin delivery or not	a.gemello
latitude of the residential address at delivery	a.lat_ok
longitude of the residential address at delivery	a.long_ok

9.3 Annex 3 – Health and contextual data for South Africa

Table 5: South Africa health variables

Variable	Variable character
Gestational age at birth (preterm birth < 37 weeks of gestation)	i_ga_m, i_ga_w, i_ga_d
Antepartum or postpartum haemorrhage	m_apc, m_apc_o, m_ppc, m_ppc_o
Maternal infection	m_ppc
Clinical events and emergency admissions in mother	cause of event/admission
Prolonged labour	i_dol_h, i_dol_m
Miscarriage	m_ppc, i_stat
Cardiovascular events	m_ppc
Hypertensive disorders	m_ppc
Mental health	m_ppc
Near-miss complications	m_ppc
Admission in intensive care	m_ref
Other obstetric complications	m_ppc
Emergency referral of women (cause of referral)	m_ref
Clinical outcomes in foetus and newborn	
Clinical events and emergency admissions	m_mod, m_ecsi
Infant measures at birth	birth weight, APGAR score, anthropometry, growth measures, other infant quality measures
Emergency admission or referral	i_ref
Complications	i_ppc
Infant care practices as indicated by mother, including exclusive breastfeeding	m_feed
Maternal and child mortality, spontaneous abortion, stillbirth	cause of death
Mode of delivery	m_mod
Emergency caesarean section	m_ecsi
Duration of labour	m_dol
Lacerations, tears, or episiotomy? Or perineum intact?	m_per

Variable	Variable character
Estimated blood loss (mL)	m_ebl
Infant abnormalities	i_abn
Date of delivery	day, month, year
Age of mother at birth	m_age
Race	m_race, m_race_o
Nationality	m_nation
Parity, gravidity, number of miscarriages	m_par, m_grav, m_mis
Alcohol consumption	self-reported composite score or consumption categories
Body mass index and other maternal anthropometry	
Antepartum complications/comorbidities	m_apc